

EXPLORING STUDENTS' SPEAKING ANXIETY AND SELF-ESTEEM: INPUTS FOR ANXIETY REDUCTION PROGRAM

Adven Shella E. Antiquando, LPT, PhD

English Department, Negros Oriental State University-Guihulngan, Guihulngan City, Negros Oriental, Philippines

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ABSTRACT

This research aims to explore students' academic self-esteem and speaking anxiety among ten groups of respondents in terms of test anxiety, communication apprehension, and fear of negative feedback as the basis for inputs in the anxiety reduction program. The respondents were grouped according to tracks, sex, and year level. The result showed that students in Junior and Senior high school in five different tracks, both male and female, of Guihulngan National High School –Poblacion experienced a moderate level of speaking anxiety. As a result, they had a moderate level of academic self-esteem. In conclusion, adding seminars and activities will lessen the students' speaking anxiety and boost their confidence, which helps them improve their academic performance. Thus, these activities will greatly help reduce speaking anxiety in the classroom, which will better benefit the respondents' speaking skills and language learning.

Keywords: *Speaking Anxiety, Academic Self-Esteem, Anxiety, Communication Apprehension, Fear of Negative Feedback, Anxiety Reduction Program*

INTRODUCTION

“Skill and confidence are an unconquered army” (George Herbert). It is best fitting to describe most personalities who excel in their best by their way of being skillful and confident. They have an abundance of ideas, and they are not hesitant in expressing them. However, it is also a common place that the greatest fear of a man is the fear of

communication. This is common to students, and there is no doubt that most learners experience different degrees of anxiety and academic self-esteem when they are asked to express themselves in front of a class or other people. In the early stages of learning a certain language, such as English, students usually face many difficulties, especially in understanding grammar, pronunciation, and other aspects. Students find it difficult, feel uncomfortable, and make mistakes. Students become anxious in speaking. After it happens repeatedly, students experience speaking anxiety in a second language (McIntyre, 1999).

On the other hand, students who are competent in learning English but think that they are not successful in the class lack self-confidence. One's confidence in realizing the goal of language learning is related to one's development of speaking skills. Speaking Anxiety affects students' academic self-esteem as students feel anxious, they lose confidence, and this builds a gap between them to succeed and excel in the class. When students experience a high level of anxiety, this decreases students' confidence and affects one's performance.

Though there were existing activities in the School, which only limited to competent and confident students, it somehow discriminated against those who were not able to build their skills and boost their confidence yet. All students must be equally exposed to activities that help them discover their strengths, develop their speaking skills, and increase their confidence, which would better benefit their class performance.

This study explored the level of speaking anxiety and academic self-esteem experienced by the students and the association of the two in both Grade 11 and 12 in five different strands.

Research Questions

This paper sets out to investigate the levels of speaking anxiety and academic self-esteem experienced among Junior High School (Grade 11) and Senior High School (Grade 12) students taking up General Academic Strand (GAS), Information and Communications Technology (ICT), Home Economics (HE), Science Technology Engineering and Mathematics (STEM), Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMSS) in Guihulngan National High School-Poblacion Guihulngan City, Negros Oriental, in terms of the three domains of speaking anxiety that usually affect students' performance (test anxiety, communication anxiety and fear of negative feedback anxiety domain) and their level of academic self-esteem (how confident they are to themselves)

This study sought to answer the following:

1. What are the profile characteristics of the students in terms of academic strand, grade level, and sex?
2. What is the level of students' speaking anxiety in terms of test anxiety, communication apprehension, and fear of negative evaluation?
3. What is the level of students' academic self-esteem?

4. Is there a significant difference in the students' level of speaking anxiety when grouped accordingly to their profile characteristics?
5. Is there a significant difference in the students' academic self-esteem when grouped accordingly to their profile characteristics?
6. Is there a significant association between students' speaking anxiety and students' self-esteem?
7. Based on the findings of the study, what anxiety reduction program can be developed to promote students' academic self-esteem?

METHODOLOGY

This study was conducted in a public secondary school located in Guihulngan City, Negros Oriental, within the first district of the province. It employed a descriptive research design to examine the level of speaking anxiety and academic self-esteem among Grade 11 and Grade 12 students enrolled in five academic strands: General Academic Strand (GAS), Home Economics (HE), Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMSS), Information and Communications Technology (ICT), and Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM). A total of 275 students participated, selected through purposive sampling based on their likelihood of experiencing speaking anxiety.

Data were gathered using two standardized instruments: the Foreign Language Classroom Anxiety Scale (FLCAS), developed by Horwitz, Horwitz, and Cope (1986), and the Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale (RSES), developed by Morris Rosenberg in 1965. The FLCAS consists of 33 items rated on a 5-point Likert scale and measures communication apprehension, test anxiety, and fear of negative evaluation. The RSES includes 9–10 items also rated on a 5-point Likert scale and assesses global self-worth. Both instruments underwent face validation through expert consultation to ensure clarity, relevance, and suitability. Data collection involved coordination with school officials and teachers, followed by classroom administration of the questionnaires with proper instructions.

The responses were encoded and analyzed using statistical software. Frequency and percentage distributions were used to describe demographic profiles, while mean scores determined levels of speaking anxiety and self-esteem. Independent t-tests and ANOVA assessed differences across demographic groups, and Pearson's *r* correlation measured the association between speaking anxiety and academic self-esteem. The study was limited to students from specific grade levels and strands during the 2018–2019 school year, and findings were based on self-reported data, which may be influenced by external factors not accounted for in the research.

RESULTS

Table 1 presents the frequency and percentage distribution of the respondents in terms of sex, grade level, and strand.

Profile	Frequency (f)	Percent (%)
Sex		
• Male	100	36.4
• Female	175	63.6
Grade Level		
• Grade 11	149	54.2
• Grade 12	126	45.8
Strand		
• GAS	58	21.1
• HE	29	10.5
• HUMSS	156	56.7
• ICT	19	6.9
• STEM	13	4.7
Total	275	100

Table 2.1 Level of Students' Speaking Anxiety

Component	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Test Anxiety	2.98	1.343	Moderately Anxious
Communication Apprehension	2.94	1.119	Moderately Anxious
Fear of Negative Evaluation	2.78	.618	Moderately Anxious
Overall	2.90	.969	Moderately Anxious

Table 2.2 Level of Students' Speaking Anxiety in terms of Test Anxiety

Indicator	Mean	Std. Deviation	Verbal Description
1. I never feel quite sure of myself when I am speaking in my foreign language class.	2.88	1.56	Moderately Anxious
2. I don't worry about making mistakes in language class.	2.91	1.48	Moderately Anxious
3. I tremble when I know that I'm going to be called on in language class.	2.97	1.47	Moderately Anxious
4. It frightens me when I don't understand what the teacher is saying in the foreign language.	2.99	1.44	Moderately Anxious

5. It wouldn't bother me at all to take more foreign language classes.	3.02	1.44	Moderately Anxious
6. During language class, I find myself thinking about things that have nothing to do with the course.	3.02	1.43	Moderately Anxious
7. I keep thinking that the other students are better at languages than I am.	3.09	1.42	Moderately Anxious
8. I am usually at ease during tests in my language class.	3.00	1.44	Moderately Anxious
9. I start to panic when I have to speak without preparation in language class.	3.04	1.47	Moderately Anxious
10. I worry about the consequences of failing my foreign language class.	2.93	1.44	Moderately Anxious
11. I don't understand why some people get so upset over foreign language classes.	2.97	1.41	Moderately Anxious
Overall	2.98	1.34	Moderately Anxious

Table 2.3 Level of Students' Speaking Anxiety in terms of Communication Apprehension

Indicator	Mean	Std. Deviation	Verbal Description
12. In language class, I can get so nervous I forget things I know.	3.10	1.43	Moderately Anxious
13. It embarrasses me to volunteer answers in my language class.	2.71	1.46	Moderately Anxious
14. I would not be nervous speaking the foreign language with native speakers.	3.50	1.31	Highly Anxious
15. I get upset when I don't understand what the teacher is correcting.	2.56	1.34	Moderately Anxious
16. Even if I am well prepared for language class, I feel anxious about it.	2.73	1.35	Moderately Anxious
17. I often feel like not going to my language class.	3.05	1.43	Moderately Anxious
18. I feel confident when I speak in foreign language class.	2.94	1.36	Moderately Anxious
19. I am afraid that my language teacher is ready to correct every mistake I make.	2.82	1.36	Moderately Anxious
20. I can feel my heart pounding when I'm going to be called on in language class.	2.81	1.33	Moderately Anxious
21. The more I study for a language test, the more confused I get.	2.94	1.37	Moderately Anxious
22. I don't feel pressure to prepare very well for language class.	3.15	1.32	Moderately Anxious
Overall	2.94	1.12	Moderately Anxious

Table 2.4 Level of Students' Speaking Anxiety in terms of Fear of Negative Evaluation

Indicator	Mean	Std. Deviation	Verbal Description
23. I always feel that the other students speak the foreign language better than I do.	2.88	1.33	Moderately Anxious
24. I feel very self-conscious about speaking the foreign language in front of other students.	2.91	1.34	Moderately Anxious
25. Language class moves so quickly I worry about getting left behind.	2.92	1.36	Moderately Anxious
26. I feel more tense and nervous in my language class than in my other classes.	2.95	1.34	Moderately Anxious
27. I get nervous and confused when I am speaking in my language class.	2.97	1.33	Moderately Anxious
28. When I'm on my way to language class, I feel very sure and relaxed.	3.49	1.25	Moderately Anxious
29. I get nervous when I don't understand every word the language teacher says.	2.18	1.24	Moderately Anxious
30. I feel overwhelmed by the number of rules you have to learn to speak a foreign language.	3.33	1.40	Moderately Anxious
31. I am afraid that the other students will laugh at me when I speak the foreign language.	1.96	1.18	Moderately Anxious
32. I would probably feel comfortable around native speakers of the foreign language.	3.42	1.36	Moderately Anxious
33. I get nervous when the language teacher asks questions which I haven't prepared in advance.	1.57	.94	Moderately Anxious
Overall	2.78	.62	Moderately Anxious

Table 3. Level of Students' Academic Self-Esteem

Indicators	Mean	Std. Deviation	Verbal Description
1. I am not as popular as people of my age	3.61	.863	High
2. I usually keep to myself because I am not liked by people of my age	3.57	.851	High
3. My parents expect too much from me	3.58	.875	High
4. My teachers expect too much from me	3.52	.885	High
5. In the kind of things we do in school I am at least as good as people in my class	2.40	.657	Moderate
6. I often feel worthless in school	3.51	.899	High
7. Most of my teachers do not understand me	3.45	.957	Moderate
8. It seems that however hard I try I never get the trade I deserve	3.48	.949	Moderate

9. School is harder for me than most other people	3.41	1.003	Moderate
10. I am frustrated when I take illegal drugs	2.27	.628	Low
11. I have as many friends as people of my age	2.38	.782	Low
12. People of my age always pick on me	2.42	.800	Low
13. Other people enjoy being in my company	2.38	.794	Low
14. Other people wish that they were like me	2.39	.856	Low
15. My parents are proud of the kind of person I am	2.28	.914	Low
16. My parents try to understand me	2.34	.930	Low
17. I am an important person to my family	2.32	.949	Low
18. My parents believe that I will be a success in the future	2.23	.938	Low
19. I am usually proud of my performance.	2.36	.969	Low
Overall	2.84	.700	Moderate

Table 4.1 Significant Difference on the Students' Level of Speaking Anxiety when Grouped according to Sex

Variable	Statistical Treatment	Test Statistic	p-value	Decision for Ho	Conclusion
Test Anxiety	Independent t-test	-3.410	.001	Reject Ho	Highly Significant
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Male (M=2.60,SD=1.480) Female (M=3.20,SD=1.210) 					
Communication Apprehension	Independent t-test	-3.961	.000	Reject Ho	Highly Significant
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Male (M=2.59,SD=1.197) Female (M=3.13,SD=1.025) 					
Fear of Negative Evaluation	Independent t-test	-2.999	.003	Reject Ho	Highly Significant
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Male(M=2.63,SD=.630) Female (M=2.86,SD=.596) 					
Speaking Anxiety	Independent t-test	-3.648	.000	Reject Ho	Highly Significant
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Male (M=2.61, SD=1.054) Female (M=3.06, SD=.879) 					

Table 4.2 Significant Difference on the Students' Level of Speaking Anxiety when Grouped according to Grade Level

Variable	Statistical Treatment	Test Statistic	p-value	Decision for Ho	Conclusion
Test Anxiety	Independent t-test	-.881	.379	Do Not Reject Ho	Not Significant
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Grade 11 (M=2.92,SD=1.338) Grade 12 (M=3.06,SD=1.350) 					
Communication Apprehension	Independent t-test	-.084	.933	Do Not Reject Ho	Not Significant
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Grade 11 (M=2.93,SD=1.136) Grade 12 (M=2.94,SD=1.103) 					
Fear of Negative Evaluation	Independent t-test	.389	.698	Do Not Reject Ho	Not Significant
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Grade 11 (M=2.79,SD=.660) Grade 12 (M=2.76,SD=.566) 					
Speaking Anxiety	Independent t-test	-.357	0.721	Do Not Reject Ho	Not Significant
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Grade 11 (M=2.88,SD=.990) 					

Table 4.3 Significant Difference on the Students' Level of Speaking Anxiety when Grouped According to Strand

Variable	Statistical Treatment	Test Statistic	p-value	Decision for Ho	Conclusion
Test Anxiety • GAS (M=2.91,SD=1.351) • HE (M=3.21,SD=1.124) • HUMSS (M=3.01,SD=1.37) • ICT (M=2.87,SD=1.448) • STEM (M=2.60,SD=1.358)	Independent t-test	.560	.692	Do Not Reject Ho	Not Significant
Communication Apprehension • GAS (M=2.92,SD=1.105) • HE (M=3.28,SD=1.077) • HUMSS (M=2.93,SD=1.142) • ICT (M=2.66,SD=1.046) • STEM (M=2.71,SD=1.055)	Independent t-test	1.142	.337	Do Not Reject Ho	Not Significant
Fear of Negative Evaluation • GAS (M=2.71,SD=0.585) • HE (M=2.84,SD=0.502) • HUMSS (M=2.82,SD=0.672) • ICT (M=2.74,SD=0.479) • STEM (M=2.57,SD=0.467)	Independent t-test	.803	.524	Do Not Reject Ho	Not Significant
Speaking Anxiety • GAS (M=2.85,SD=0.949) • HE (M=3.11,SD=0.837) • HUMSS (M=2.92,SD=1.009) • ICT (M=2.76,SD=0.942) • STEM (M=2.63,SD=0.901)	Independent t-test	.772	.544	Do Not Reject Ho	Not Significant

Table 5. Significant Difference in the Students' Self-Esteem when Grouped According to Profile

Variable	Statistical Treatment	Test Statistic	p-value	Decision for Ho	Conclusion
Sex • Male (M=2.97,SD=.728) • Female (M=2.76,SD=.672)	Independent t-test	2.489	0.013	Reject Ho	Significant
Grade Level • Grade 11 (M=2.87,SD=.728) • Grade 12 (M=2.80,SD=.666)	Independent t-test	.846	0.398	Do Not Reject Ho	Not Significant
Strand • GAS (M=2.83,SD=.637) • HE (M=2.74,SD=.647) • HUMSS (M=2.82,SD=.739) • ICT (M=2.98,SD=.726)	ANOVA	.597	.665	Do Not Reject Ho	Not Significant

- STEM
(M=3.02,SD=.569)

Table 6. Association between Students' Speaking Anxiety and Self-esteem

Self-esteem VS	Pearson-r Value	Strength of Correlation	Nature of Association	p-Value	Decision for Ho	Conclusion
Test Anxiety	-.814	High Correlation	Indirect Association/ Negative Correlation	0.000	Reject Ho	Highly Significant
Communication Apprehension	-.771	High Correlation	Indirect Association/ Negative Correlation	0.000	Reject Ho	Highly Significant
Fear of Negative Evaluation	-.684	Moderately High Correlation	Indirect Association/ Negative Correlation	0.000	Reject Ho	Highly Significant
Speaking Anxiety	-.818	High Correlation	Indirect Association/ Negative Correlation	0.000	Reject Ho	Highly Significant

DISCUSSION

The results presented in Table 1 reveal that when respondents were classified according to sex, there were more female students than males. Additionally, more than half of the participants were in Grade 11, and the majority belonged to the HUMSS strand, comprising 56.7% of the total sample. Table 2.1 outlines the students' speaking anxiety across three domains: test anxiety, communication apprehension, and fear of negative evaluation. Overall, students exhibited moderate levels of anxiety in oral communication, with consistent ratings across all three domains, indicating a uniform experience of anxiety during speaking tasks. To gain deeper insight into test anxiety, Table 2.2 provides detailed indicators. Students reported a mean score of 2.98 with a standard deviation of 1.34, suggesting moderate anxiety. However, the highest anxiety was observed when students were asked to speak without preparation, often leading to panic and self-comparison with peers they perceived as more competent.

Table 2.3 highlights students' experiences with communication apprehension. It was found that students felt highly anxious when speaking with native speakers, often forgetting what they knew due to nervousness, which sometimes led to avoidance of language classes. In addition to communication challenges, students were also concerned about receiving negative feedback from peers and teachers. Table 2.4 illustrates their fear of negative evaluation, showing moderate anxiety levels, particularly when interacting with native speakers and navigating complex language rules, which made them feel uncertain and tense. Across nine to ten indicators, students generally exhibited low academic self-esteem.

To determine differences in speaking anxiety based on demographic variables, independent t-tests were conducted. Results showed a highly significant difference in speaking anxiety between male and female students ($t = -3.648$, $p = 0.000$), with females experiencing higher levels of anxiety across all domains. However, no significant difference was found between Grade 11 and Grade 12 students ($t = -0.357$, $p = 0.721$), indicating similar anxiety levels across grade levels. ANOVA results also showed no significant difference in speaking anxiety among students from different strands ($F = 0.772$, $p = 0.544$), suggesting that the academic strand does not influence speaking anxiety.

Regarding self-esteem, independent t-tests revealed a significant difference between male and female students ($t = 2.49$, $p = 0.013$), with males reporting higher self-esteem. No significant difference was found between grade levels ($t = 0.846$, $p = 0.398$), nor among academic strands ($F = 0.597$, $p = 0.665$), indicating consistent self-esteem levels across these groups. Pearson correlation analysis showed a strong negative relationship between speaking anxiety and self-esteem ($r = -0.818$, $p = 0.000$), meaning that higher anxiety corresponds to lower self-esteem and vice versa. This pattern held across all domains—test anxiety, communication apprehension, and fear of negative evaluation—each negatively correlated with self-esteem.

These findings align with prior research. Kalanzadeh et al. (2012) found that highly self-confident students were more likely to engage in classroom conversations and oral activities. Krashen's (1982) affective filter hypothesis, as cited in De Bot et al. (2005), emphasizes that students who can avoid negative attitudes such as anxiety and low confidence are more likely to succeed in second language acquisition. Brown (2007) advocates for building self-confidence by affirming students' abilities and encouraging reflection on their strengths and achievements. Mak (2011) also stresses the importance of addressing students' psychological needs alongside linguistic competence. Brown further identifies self-confidence as a core principle of language teaching, asserting that belief in one's ability is central to learning success. When students believe they can accomplish tasks, self-confidence motivates them to persevere and achieve, making it a key factor in effective language learning.

Conclusions

The study concludes that students generally experience moderate speaking anxiety, particularly when asked to speak without preparation, interact with native speakers, or face potential negative feedback from peers and teachers—factors that significantly impact their academic self-esteem. Female students were found to have higher levels of speaking anxiety than males, while no significant differences were observed across grade levels or academic strands. Similarly, male students exhibited higher self-esteem, but grade level and strand did not influence self-esteem levels. A strong negative correlation was identified between speaking anxiety and self-esteem, indicating that increased anxiety leads to decreased confidence. These findings highlight the importance of creating supportive, inclusive, and psychologically aware language classrooms. Teachers should recognize and address individual anxieties, foster positive

learning environments, and involve all students in speaking activities to help build their confidence. Effective strategies such as humor, encouragement, and relaxed error correction can reduce anxiety and enhance self-esteem, ultimately improving students' performance and engagement in language learning.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, it is recommended that language teachers create a more inclusive and supportive classroom environment that actively addresses speaking anxiety and fosters academic self-esteem. Teachers should be trained to recognize signs of anxiety and implement strategies such as positive reinforcement, relaxed error correction, and engaging speaking activities that encourage participation from all students, not just those who are already confident. Existing school programs should be expanded to include seminars, workshops, and task-based presentations that allow students to discover and develop their speaking skills. Since female students exhibited higher levels of anxiety and lower self-esteem, targeted interventions may be necessary to support their emotional and academic needs. Additionally, future research is encouraged to explore speaking anxiety and self-esteem using larger and more diverse samples, possibly across different regions or educational settings. Studies employing qualitative approaches may also provide deeper insights into students' personal experiences and coping mechanisms. If any results appear unexpected or inconsistent, further investigation should be conducted to validate the findings and uncover underlying causes.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher affirms that all ethical standards were strictly observed throughout the conduct of this study. Informed consent was obtained from all respondents before their participation, and they were assured of their right to withdraw from the study at any point without consequence. The anonymity and confidentiality of all participants were maintained, and their well-being was safeguarded during the data collection process. There was no conflict of interest involved in the execution of the research. Plagiarism was strictly avoided, and all sources were properly acknowledged. The interpretation of findings was conducted without bias, and the results were used solely for academic and research purposes.

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